

Food demand in six EU countries

The Challenge

Developing an effective policy to steer consumers towards more sustainable diets requires an understanding food preferences and drivers of food demand. Food preferences change over time and have been shown to be culturally/regionally specific, and there is a paucity of demand studies that have analysed entire diets. In order to address this knowledge gap, this study analysed food demand in six EU countries (UK, France, Spain, Italy, Finland and Sweden).

Policy Implication

Consumers respond to prices, and the law of demand applies to all foods at a fairly high level of product disaggregation. Second, most food products are necessities, as their demand responds positively but less than proportionally to changes in consumption expenditure. Third, for all countries, some cross-price elasticities are both statistically significant and relatively large, which confirms the necessity of considering whole diets rather than only subsets of foods when analysing policies to enhance the sustainability of food consumption patterns.

Research

The analysis used household-level data on food consumption in year 2012, which were first aggregated into 20 common categories chosen based on an assessment of health and climate impact. For each participating household, the data gave a weekly account of all foods purchased for at-home consumption, including product characteristics at barcode level e.g. brand, size, price and quantity.

Results

Price increases result in a decrease of demand for the same category. For example, in the UK a 10% increase of the price “Vegetables”, “Fruits”, “Soft drinks” and “Sugar and Desserts” categories will result in a decrease of the demand for these four categories by 5%, 8%, 9% and 11%, respectively.

An increase in price results in a less than proportional decrease in demand, with some exceptions both in terms of product categories and countries. Overall, the findings were consistent with a growing body of literature on fat and sugar taxes, which establishes that, to have any effect on diets, price incentives need to exceed 10% or even 20%.

Food demand in six EU countries

By Michael Hays - Flickr, CC BY 2.0,
<https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=3031790>

Funding

Scottish Government's Rural and Environment Science and Analytical Services Division (RESAS)

UK Department of Food Environment of Rural Affairs (Defra)

Scottish Funding Council supported Universities Innovation Fund

Scottish Government
Riaghaltas na h-Alba
gov.scot

Contact

Contact: Cesar Revoredo

Email: cesar.revoredo@sruc.ac.uk

Research group: Land Economy, Environment and Society

Address: SRUC, Peter Wilson Building, Edinburgh, EH9 3JG.

About

The Land Economy, Environment and Society (LEES) Research Group is one of the largest groupings of economists and social scientists working in the rural, agricultural and land based sectors in the UK. Our vision is to be recognised as one of the leading centres for agricultural and wider rural economic and social research globally, benefiting the land use sector, the environment and rural communities.

Leading the way in Agriculture and Rural Research, Education and Consulting

SRUC is a charity registered in Scotland, No. SC003712